

Time of application of organic matter and humic acid on transformation of inorganic and organic forms of N in soil

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Abstract : Irrespective of treatments and stages of incubation, comparatively higher amount of available N is accumulated in soil treated either with FYM or humic acid 21 days before than on the day of start of the experiment. Humic acid is decomposed faster than FYM leading to higher amount of accumulation of available N in humic acid treated system. In general, irrespective of treatments, hydrolysable NH_4^+ increased over 120 days period of incubation and the amount of increase is more in soil treated either with FYM or humic acid on the day of start of the experiment. However, a reverse trend of results is obtained for amino acid N in soil. Hydrolysable NH_4^+ and amino acid N are more prone to mineralization than any other organic forms of N in soil.

Keywords : Humic acid, FYM, time of application, N transformation.

Introduction

Nitrogen (N) is a major component of chlorophyll, by which plants use sunlight energy to produce sugars from water and carbon dioxide¹. It is also a major component of amino acids, the building blocks of proteins². Some proteins act as structural units in plant cells while others act as enzymes, making possible many of the biochemical reactions on which life is based. Nitrogen is also a significant component of nucleic acids such as DNA, the genetic material that allows cells (and eventually whole plants) to grow and reproduce. The liberation pattern of N from native as well as applied organic sources is not only controlled by the environmental conditions but also by management practices³.

It is well known that soil organic matter (SOM) is the main source of indigenous soil N supply and a number of studies have documented a positive relationship between SOM concentration and soil N-supplying capacity⁴. The resistant portion of the soil or-

ganic matter is humus which plays an important role in soil-forming processes and soil fertility. Because of the complexity of the soil-humus, a comprehensive study of this subject is of utmost importance. Nitrogen present in humus can serve as a slow-release source of nitrogen^{5,6}. The N content of humic acid varies from 1 to 5% depending upon its origin and sources of organic matter⁷. The organic form of nitrogen is not directly available to plants, but some can be converted to available forms by microorganisms. The majority of plant-available nitrogen is in the inorganic forms i.e. NH_4^+ and NO_3^- .

Organic matter as N source is well known⁸ but humic acid application to soil as a source of N has not been explicitly investigated. Addition of either organic matter or humic acid in soil influences N transformation^{9,10}. Addition of organic matter to soil before a cropping season is helpful in maintaining N pool in soil. Release of N from any organic source in soil depends on the time of its application in soil. Farmers

normally apply organic matter in soil 2–3 weeks before the sowing of crop so that the organic matter gets ample time to mineralize and release different nutrients for plant uptake. Organic matter also releases humic acid, fulvic acid into the soil system. Humic acid contains significant amount of N which upon mineralization serves as a source for plant uptake. If humic acid extracted from the organic matter can be applied just before the sowing of crop immediately N can be available to plants.

Keeping above information in view, an attempt has been made to study the effect of time of application of organic matter as well as humic acid on transformation of different forms of inorganic and organic N in soil.

Experimental

Site characters and soil sampling :

Soil sample was collected after harvesting of jute from 0–15 cm soil depth located in Pundibari block in the district of Cooch Behar, West Bengal, India. The cropping system was rice-jute continuing for the last 15 years. The area is situated at 26°19' N latitude and 89°23' E longitude with an altitude of 43 m above msl. The study area comes under tropical and sub-

humid to humid type of climate, with annual mean maximum and minimum temperatures of 32.5 °C and 20.2 °C, respectively. Mean annual rainfall is 3201 mm, which is characterized by heavy rainfall during the monsoon and slight rainfall in the month of October to mid-November. The collected soil sample was air dried, ground with a mortar and pestle and sieved through a 2 mm sieve and stored in a plastic container for the incubation experiment. The soil was classified as *Aquic ustifluvent*¹¹. The physical and chemical properties of the soil are presented in Table 1.

Experimental design :

The incubation experiment was conducted in a completely randomized factorial design with three replications. The applications consist of farm yard manure (FYM) at 5 tons ha⁻¹, humic acid (HA) equivalent to FYM on the basis of N content and nitrogen as urea at 150 kg ha⁻¹. Humic acid was extracted from the FYM with 0.5 N NaOH¹².

Six treatments were employed as follows :

T₁ = Soil, T₂ = Soil + N at 75 mg kg⁻¹, T₃ = Soil + FYM at 2.5 g kg⁻¹, T₄ = Soil + FYM at 2.5 g kg⁻¹ + N at 75 mg kg⁻¹, T₅ = Soil + HA equivalent to FYM on N basis, T₆ = Soil + HA equivalent to FYM on N basis + N at 75 mg kg⁻¹.

Table 1. Some physico-chemical properties of the soil used in the experiment

Properties	Quantities	Methods adopted
Mechanical separates		Hydrometer method ²⁴
Sand (%)	54.6	
Silt (%)	42.0	
Clay (%)	3.4	
Textural class	Sandy loam	
USDA classification	<i>Aquic ustifluvent</i>	11
pH	7.35	} 25
EC (dSm ⁻¹)	0.114	
Oxidizable Organic Carbon (%)	0.91	26
Available P ₂ O ₅ (kg ha ⁻¹)	132.8	} 25
Available K ₂ O (kg ha ⁻¹)	114	
Exchangeable NH ₄ ⁺ (mg kg ⁻¹)	77.89	} 27
Soluble NO ₃ ⁻ (mg kg ⁻¹)	47.93	
Hydrolysable NH ₄ ⁺ -N (mg kg ⁻¹)	176.96	
Amino acid N (mg kg ⁻¹)	199.08	
Total hydrolysable organic N (mg kg ⁻¹)	530.88	
Total nitrogen (mg kg ⁻¹)	982.34	

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The experiment was conducted with 10 g of soil in 100 ml beaker. There were two sets of same treatments for two different times of application of organic matters. In the 1st set organic matter either FYM or humic acid was added 21 days before the start of experiment. In the 2nd set FYM or humic acid was added on the day of start of the experiment. Nitrogen as urea at 75 mg kg⁻¹ was added to all the N-treated systems as basal dose. Separate sets were maintained for identical collection of soil samples on 15th, 45th, 75th and 120th day of the experiment. Soils were maintained at 60% of water holding capacity and kept at room temperature (26 ± 2 °C) throughout the experimentation period. The loss of moisture due to evaporation was replenished by periodic addition of sterile distilled water on every alternate day by difference in weight.

Soil sampling and analysis :

Soils were sampled on 15th, 45th, 75th and 120th day of the experiment for analysis of different fractions of inorganic and organic N. Potassium chloride (2 M KCl) solution was employed for extraction of exchangeable NH₄⁺ and soluble NO₃⁻-N and was estimated following standard method¹³. Both NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻ together were represented as available N in the text. Different fractions of organic N, viz. hydrolysable NH₄⁺-N, amino acid N, and hexosamine-N were determined¹⁴.

Statistical analysis :

Data of inorganic and organic N were statistically analyzed following Microsoft Excel and SPSS Window version 17.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA) packages. Duncan's multiple range test (DMRT) at 5% level of probability was used to test the difference between means of individual treatments¹⁵.

Results and discussion

Irrespective of treatments, significantly higher amount of available N is accumulated in soil treated with organic matter 21 days before the start of experiment upto 15th day of the incubation (Table 2). However, a completely reverse trend of results is observed on 45th day of experiment. Accumulation of available N is comparatively more in soil treated with organic matter 21 days before than on the day of start of the experiment on 75th day of the incubation. But at the last stage, the treatment difference is negligible with respect to available N accumulation in soil. In general, addition of organic matter either in the form of FYM or humic acid increased available N content in soils. Furthermore, in general, accumulation of available N is comparatively more in humic acid than FYM treated system particularly upto 75th day of incubation. Humic acid is decomposed faster than FYM¹⁶ leading to higher amount of accumulation of available

Table 2. Effect of time of application of FYM vis-à-vis humic acid on changes in the amount (mg kg⁻¹) of available nitrogen in soil

Treatment	Incubation period (Days)							
	15		45		75		120	
	D ₁	D ₂	D ₁	D ₂	D ₁	D ₂	D ₁	D ₂
T ₁	152.7e	95.9c	139.8e	231.7e	361.6b	153.3c	154.3d	171.3c
T ₂	219.7c	133.8b	207.7b	297.6c	337.6c	207.4a	201.4b	213.4ab
T ₃	177.8d	99.9c	163.8d	253.7d	245.7f	135.2d	174.3c	163.0cd
T ₄	315.6a	159.8a	219.7a	381.5a	401.5a	191.3b	222.4a	222.4a
T ₅	289.6b	105.8c	183.7c	299.6c	277.6e	144.3cd	150.3d	153.3d
T ₆	324.5a	159.5a	213.7ab	317.8b	311.6d	192.3b	201.4b	198.3b
Mean	246.6	125.8	188.1	297.0	322.6	170.6	184.0	186.9

D₁ : FYM/Humic acid applied 21 days before the start of experiment, D₂ : FYM/Humic acid applied on 0th day of the experiment.

T₁ : Soil, T₂ : Soil + Nitrogen (Urea @ 75 mg kg⁻¹), T₃ : Soil + Farm Yard Manure @ 2.5 g kg⁻¹, T₄ : Soil + Farm Yard Manure @ 2.5 g kg⁻¹ + Nitrogen (Urea @ 75 mg kg⁻¹), T₅ : Soil + Humic Acid, T₆ : Soil + Humic Acid + Nitrogen (Urea @ 75 mg kg⁻¹), T = Treatments, D = Time of application of FYM/Humic acid.

Values with different lower case (a-f) letters are significantly different at P < 0.05 (at 5% level of significance) according to Duncan multiple range tests for separation of mean.

N in humic acid treated systems. The effect of added inorganic N is prominent throughout the experimentation period^{17,18}.

Results of hydrolysable NH_4^+ presented in Figs. 1a and 1b revealed that comparatively higher amount of hydrolysable NH_4^+ is accumulated in soil treated either with FYM or humic acid 21 days before than on 0th day of the experiment upto 15th day of the incubation study. However, a reverse trend of results was observed on 45th day onwards to last stage of the experiment. Soils received either FYM or humic acid on the day of start of the experiment showed different trend of results (Figs. 1a and 1b). Accumulation of hydrolysable NH_4^+ -N progressively increased upto 45th then decreased on 75th but again increased on 120th day i.e. last stage of experiment. The difference in accumulation of hydrolysable NH_4^+ -N might be due to addition of organic matter to soil at different times of the experiment. The increase or decrease in accumulation of hydrolysable NH_4^+ in soil during the incubation period might be due to mineralization and immobilization of organic N. Critical examination of the results (Figs. 1a and 1b) revealed that in general, irrespective of treatments, hydrolysable NH_4^+ -N increased over 120 day period of incubation and the amount of increase is more in soil treated either with FYM or humic acid on the day of start of experiment. Thus the results show that hydrolysable NH_4^+ is mineralized at a faster rate in soil treated with organic matters 21 days before than that on 0th day of the experiment. The effect of time of application on N-mineralization has been reported earlier¹⁰. Closer examination of the data further revealed that in general comparatively higher amount of hydrolysable NH_4^+ is accumulated in soil treated with humic acid than that of FYM particularly at the early stage of incubation. The effect of added inorganic N on accumulation of comparatively higher amount of hydrolysable NH_4^+ in soil is prominent upto 15th day of incubation. However, at the last stage of incubation, no definite trend of results is observed with regard to effect of added inorganic N. The variation in accumulation of hydrolysable NH_4^+ in N treated and untreated systems is due to addition of organic matter at different

Fig. 1a. Changes in the amount of hydrolysable ammonium (NH_4^+) in soil treated with FYM vis-à-vis humic acid 21 days before the start of experiment. T₁ : Soil, T₂ : Soil + Nitrogen (Urea @ 75 mg kg⁻¹), T₃ : Soil + Farm Yard Manure @ 2.5 g kg⁻¹, T₄ : Soil + Farm Yard Manure @ 2.5 g kg⁻¹ + Nitrogen (Urea @ 75 mg kg⁻¹), T₅ : Soil + Humic Acid, T₆ : Soil + Humic Acid + Nitrogen (Urea @ 75 mg kg⁻¹).

Fig. 1b. Changes in the amount of hydrolysable ammonium (NH_4^+) in soil treated with FYM vis-à-vis humic acid on 0th day of the experiment. Six treatments (T₁-T₆) same as Fig. 1a.

stages of the incubation study^{19,10}. The addition of organic matter at different stages influences the mineralization of FYM or humic acid and also immobilization of added inorganic N in a soil system²⁰.

Hexosamine form of organic N did not play any significant role in N transformation process. No definite trend of results is obtained with respect to treatments and time of application of organic matters (Table 3). Addition of FYM or humic acid at different stages

Table 3. Effect of time of application of FYM vis-à-vis humic acid on changes in the amount (mg kg⁻¹) of hexosamine nitrogen in soil

Treatment	Incubation period (Days)							
	15		45		75		120	
	D ₁	D ₂	D ₁	D ₂	D ₁	D ₂	D ₁	D ₂
T ₁	45.1ab	44.2a	59.9a	29.5bc	45.1a	22.7a	45.1a	22.7a
T ₂	45.1ab	22.1c	30.0c	22.1c	45.1a	22.7a	45.1a	22.7a
T ₃	45.1ab	36.9b	44.2b	28.8bc	45.1a	22.7a	40.2a	22.7a
T ₄	30.0b	36.9b	30.0c	22.1c	40.2a	22.7a	45.1a	22.7a
T ₅	49.9a	22.1c	59.9a	45.4a	45.1a	25.4a	45.1a	25.4a
T ₆	30.0b	36.9b	40.0bc	35.0b	45.1a	22.7a	45.1a	22.7a
Mean	40.8	33.2	44.0	30.5	44.3	23.1	44.3	23.1

Data : Same as Table 2.

of the experiment had little effect on the accumulation of hexosamine N in soil. It is also note worthy to mention that the amount of hexosamine N with respect to other forms of organic N is so meagre that this form did not influence the N-transformation process to a great extent²¹.

Irrespective of treatments, amino acid N increased initially but thereafter decreased on 45th day of the experiment (Figs. 2a and 2b). However, the amount of amino acid N again increased on 75th but thereafter decreased at the last stage of incubation. This increase and decrease in the amount of amino acid N in soil clearly pointed out that amino acid N is subjected to mineralization and immobilization during a cropping season. The results are in agreement with earlier works^{22,23}. The time of application of organic matter did not affect the mineralization and immobilization pattern of amino acid N in soil (Figs. 2a and 2b). In general, comparatively higher amount of amino acid N is accumulated in soil treated either with FYM or humic acid 21 days before than on the day of start of the experiment. This trend of results is, in general, observed throughout the period of investigation. Furthermore, irrespective of the time of application of organic matter, comparatively higher amount of amino acid is mineralized from humic acid than FYM treated soils particularly at the later period of incubation. Irrespective of treatments, effect of added inorganic N

Fig. 2a. Changes in the amount of amino acid N in soil treated with FYM vis-à-vis humic acid 21 days before the start of experiment. Six treatments (T₁-T₆) same as Fig. 1.

Fig. 2b. Changes in the amount of amino acid N in soil treated with FYM vis-à-vis humic acid on 0th day of the experiment. Six treatments (T₁-T₆) same as Fig. 1.

is prominent through out the experimentation period. The result of N effect on amino acid accumulation supports the previous research²³.

Conclusion

Addition of FYM or humic acid showed more or less similar trend of results on changes in different forms of inorganic and organic N in soil. Application of FYM or humic acid 21 days before the start of experiment leads to accumulate higher amount of available N in soil. Irrespective of time of application, humic acid is more prone to N-mineralization than that of FYM. It is considered that bulky FYM can be replaced by humic acid, particularly with respect to release of N from organic sources.

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